

Covid 19 Outcome in Relation to Obesity-A Narrative Review.

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Citation: Dalia Biswas, Covid 19 outcome in relation to Obesity-A Narrative Review. *Int Clinc Med Case Rep Jour.* 2023;2(15):1-8. DOI:

Received Date: 11 September, 2023; **Accepted Date:** 16 September, 2023; **Published Date:** 19 September, 2023

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ABSTRACT

This review was taken up with the objective of studying the association between obesity and coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) outcomes. Databases like MEDLINE, EMBASE, Scopus, Web of Science, CENTRAL, Open Grey were searched for evidences to find association between obesity and COVID-mortality and other outcomes from December 2019 to December 2021. Total 168 eligible studies were identified out of which 130 studies were found applicable for this review.

Subjects with a higher degree of obesity faces a greater risk of developing the adverse outcomes due to COVID-19. This review from multiple studies concludes that, there exists an association between obesity and COVID-19 outcome but their relation to mortality is unclear.

Keywords: COVID-19; Obesity; ICU

INTRODUCTION & BACKGROUND

The prevalence of obesity has almost tripled in the last four decades contributing to 13% of the entire world's adult population as per WHO^[1], which was a cause for concern during the COVID-19 outbreak. Obesity is defined as excessive fat accumulation in different parts of the human body which is a risk to health. Obesity assessment is done with body mass index (BMI) measurements. Weight in kilograms divided by the square of height in metres is used to calculate BMI. The WHO has classified obesity into three groups. In this classification, class I obesity BMI ranging from 30 to 35 kg/m² is class I obesity, BMI from 35 to 40 kg/m² is class II and class III BMI is 40 kg/m² and above.

COVID-19 pandemic began in December 2019, when pneumonia of unknown origin was diagnosed in Hubei province, Wuhan, China^[2,3]. Although this disease affected multiple systems, obesity was identified as one of the major comorbid factors in sufferers of COVID-19^[4-13]. In this pandemic, due to lockdowns lasting several months, flexible work routine, increased food intake, lack of exercise, and stress due to the disease there was a high risk of gaining weight and developing obesity^[14].

The relation between obesity and other disease conditions has been established since long. These comorbid determinants have been shown to have a relation with increased predisposition and severity of COVID-19^[15-18]. There are many studies which have reported increased incidences of hospitalization, mechanical ventilation, and mortality in cases with a higher BMI^[19-23]. Berrington de Gonzalez et al. (2010) studied the relation between overweight and obesity on mortality in 1.46 million white adults over a 10 years median follow-up period. This study showed a linear relationship in the hazard ratios for BMI. In the BMI range of 25 kg/m² to 49.9 kg/m² the hazard ratio for every 5-unit increment of BMI was 1.31^[24]. The 2017-2018 National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey (NHANES) reports 42.5% of U.S. adults are obese and around 9% have severe obesity or class 3 obesity (BMI 40 kg/m² or more)^[25].

The common determinants of Obesity found were physical inactivity increasing sedentary, eating unhealthy foods, high level of stress, anxiety, depression and educational status and ethnicity.

Physical inactivity was the most common identified factor during the COVID-19 lockdown. This determinant is associated with weight gain and obesity during the quarantine period^[26-42] increasing sedentary behavior which is defined as low levels of energy expenditure during sitting or lying down. Sedentary behaviour played a great role in inducing obesity during the pandemic^[26,43,44-48], and eating unhealthy foods which is defined as eating more calories and high added sugar food^[43,49-51].

Increased stress, anxiety and depression activates brain hormones, such as cortisol, which in turn increases hunger leading to increased weight gain. Specific studies included fear of COVID-19^[52], anxiety^[52], increased stress^[51-52], poor mood development^[53], and depression^[52,51,53].

Educational status and ethnicity was also identified as a risk factor for weight gain during the lockdown. Those educated gained less weight compared to those who were less educated^[49-52].

This narrative review aims to find out whether obesity had any effects on hospitalisation, ICU admission and mortality, due to COVID-19 disease.

METHODS

Medical databases like MEDLINE, EMBASE, Scopus, Web of Science, CENTRAL, OpenGrey were searched for evidences to find association between obesity and COVID-mortality and other outcomes from December 2019 to December 2021.

Total 168 eligible studies were identified out of which 130 studies were found applicable for this review. Search terms used were: “Overweight” OR “Obesity” OR “BMI,” AND “mortality related to COVID-19” OR “death related to COVID-19”.

The final included studies were observational with targeted outcome indicators which included positive COVID test results, hospitalization, ICU admission, invasive mechanical ventilation, and in-hospital mortality. Intensive care unit (ICU) admission or critical disease, severe disease and mortality were the primary outcomes of this study. A positive COVID-19 test and increased risk of mortality among class I, class II, and class III obesity. was taken as the secondary outcome.

DISCUSSION

This review highlights the linear relation of obesity and SARS-CoV-2. Obese COVID-19 patients had more chances to be hospitalized requiring ICU admission and invasive mechanical ventilation (IMV). There are certain limitations of studies included in this review. The included studies had different standards of implementation for hospitalization, ICU admission, IMV affecting the reliability of studies. Second, the types of studies are mainly retrospective, which included case-control studies and cohort studies. This may affect the reliability of conclusions. Third, in most of the studies BMI ranges were not consistent. This may affect the reliability and extrapolation of the results. Fourth, only studies in English literature were selected, which may lead to the deletion of related non-English literature affecting the final conclusion's reliability.

Tamara et al^[54] found that obesity significantly increases the risk of severe conditions in COVID-19 patients. In their three retrospective cohort studies^[55] found significantly higher cases of COVID-19 patients with severe conditions associated with increased BMI than those with mild conditions.

Pranata et al^[56] observed a higher BMI in association with increased risk of death, and critical illness. Hussain et al studied association between BMI > 25 kg/m² and COVID-19 end point outcomes namely. critical illness, need for respiratory support and mortality. They found a significant correlation between them^[57].

Földi et al^[58] compared the risk of receiving IMV in different BMI ranges of COVID-19 patients. They found obesity as a risk factor for ICU admission and IMV therapy. They also found that a higher BMI indicates a higher risk of receiving IMV when they compared the risk of receiving IMV in different BMI ranges of COVID-19 patients.

Malik et al^[59] in their of retrospective case-control studies have observed the prevalence of COVID-19 to be to 0.34 among patients with BMI > 25 kg/m² and 0.60 among patients with BMI < 25 kg/m². This was a small

sample study and hence credibility needs further validation. Most of these studies adopted composite endpoints, so assessment of the impact of obesity on the risk of specific single endpoint events was difficult.

A meta-analysis published in the latest issue of Obesity Reviews did a systematic evaluation of outcome indicators of COVID-19 patients having obesity^[60]. This study had a strict BMI segmentation points used for comparing the risk of five outcome events in COVID-19 patients with varying BMI ranges. To decrease the impact of other factors on mortality, the index of in-hospital mortality was used rather than overall mortality.

Obesity and associated metabolic syndrome can cause potential damages to some organs like lung and kidney specially making them more prone to dysfunction^[61]. Obese patients were likely to bear the brunt of COVID-19 due to many factors. Obesity could increase the expression of ACE2- and CD147-related genes in the bronchus and blood which have receptors for SARS-CoV-2 to invade. Obesity increases the likelihood of their expression^[62]. Hence obese subjects are more prone to infection and have a higher positive test rate of SARS-CoV-2. Also due to the increased expression of ACE2 in obese subjects, adipose tissues are more likely to become the site of virus stagnation which can decrease virus removal and worsen the infection^[63]. This infection caused by obesity is also likely to damage the immune system making it abnormal in SARS-Cov-2. Obesity leads to increased pressure in chest and abdomen, which decreases the expansion of the lungs^[64]. This explains the proneness of obese patients having COVID-19 to respiratory distress and subsequently requiring mechanical ventilation. All these factors explains the likelihood of obese patients to get infected with SARS-Cov-2 and develop more severity after the infection.

CONCLUSION

Enough evidences are there to point the relation between extreme obesity (BMI > 40 kg/m²) and increased chances of hospitalisation, requirement of mechanical ventilation, ICU admission and in-hospital mortality of hospitalized COVID-19 patients.

Subjects with a higher degree of obesity faces a greater risk of developing the above mentioned adverse outcomes. Rigorous basic and clinical therapeutic research regarding this aggravation are required.

This review from multiple studies concludes that there exists an association between obesity and COVID-19 outcome but their relation to mortality is unclear.

CONFLICTS OF INTEREST

Author declares that there are no conflicts of interest.

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